

Methane, a gasocrine signal, is likely sensed via methanol-sensing alcohol receptors

Savani Anbalagan^{1,2}

¹Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology, Faculty of Biology, Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznań, Poland.

²Correspondence

E-mail: savani.anbalagan@amu.edu.pl

Tel: +48 61 829 5905

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DRAFT

Understanding how organisms communicate is a fundamental question in biology and marks an evolutionarily important milestone. Organisms largely communicate via gas-based gasocrine, light-based photocrine, sound-based sonocrine, mineral/metal-based metallochrine, water-based aquacrine, and thermal radiation-based thermocrine signaling. Due to the importance of gasocrine signaling for biotic life, how organisms can sense gasocrine signals such as O₂ (oxygen) via O₂-sensing protein gasoreceptors (or sensors) has been largely investigated in microorganisms. Even though, methane is also one of the gasocrine signals, to the best of my knowledge and few other experts on chemistry (including a Nobel laureate in Chemistry) and methanotrophic organisms, how organisms sense methane *per se* is still unknown. In my opinion, just as the heme or iron-sulfur cluster cofactor is involved in sensing O₂ in gasoreceptors such as DosP (Direct Oxygen Sensor) or FNR (fumarate and nitrate reduction transcriptional regulator) in bacteria, other cofactors that can bind methane *per se* may mediate methane-based gasocrine signaling via methane-sensing gasoreceptors. Additionally, similar to how lactose levels are sensed as allolactose via the lac repressor (a sugar-sensing swodkoreceptor), methane may also be sensed as methanol via alcohol-sensing receptors. Identifying how cells sense methane *per se* or methanol may help us understand gasocrine signaling, causes for civilizational diseases, and/or challenges due to rising methane levels on planet earth.